

Temporal localized Turing patterns in mode-locked semiconductor lasers

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Spatiotemporal mode-locking is a promising lasing regime for developing coherent sources for multimode nonlinear photonics. In this paper we show that large-aspect-ratio vertical external-cavity surface-emitting lasers (VECSELs) can be operated in this regime. The emitted pulses exhibit a spatial profile resulting from the phase locking between an axial plane wave and a set of tilted waves having a hexagonal arrangement in the Fourier space. Moreover, we show that these pulsating patterns are temporally localized, i.e., they can be individually addressed by pulsing the optical pump. The theoretical analysis discloses that the emergence of these pulsating patterns is a signature of a Turing instability whose critical wave vector depends on the spherical aberrations of the optical elements. Our result reveals that large-aspect-ratio VECSELs offer unique opportunities for studying fully developed spatiotemporal dynamics and for applications to multidimensional control of light.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Large-aspect-ratio (large Fresnel number) lasers [1,2] are a playground for studying pattern formation ruled by paradigmatic partial differential equations (PDEs) [3–8]. A variety of dissipative structures have been experimentally reported as the result of self-organization, including phase singularities [9,10], Turing instabilities [11], and, in bistable laser cavities, localized structures (LSs) [12–16]. The latter, in particular, have attracted a lot of attention in the last 30 years for their application to information processing [17]. LSs in optical resonators [18–21], often called cavity solitons, are narrow beams of light appearing in the transverse section of a resonator that can be individually switched on and off by a local perturbation [22].

More recently, the concept of LSs has been extended to the time domain: temporal LSs are individually addressable pulses traveling back and forth inside the cavity [23–27]. In semiconductor lasers, temporal LSs have been implemented within the regime of passive mode-locking (PML) induced by a saturable absorber [28–30]. It has been shown that, if the cavity roundtrip τ is larger than the gain recovery τ_g and above a critical modulation depth of the saturable absorber, a variety of mode-locked states with a different number of pulses per roundtrip coexist with the off solution. In these conditions, mode-locked pulses become localized, and they can be individually addressed.

Temporal LSs have so far been implemented in laser cavities emitting on a single-transverse mode operation. However, it was recently shown that passively mode-locked vertical external-cavity surface-emitting lasers (VECSEL) are promising candidates for fulfilling both the large-aspect-ratio condition and the requirements for temporal localization [31]. A VECSEL featuring these properties would be a laser platform ideally suited for the analysis of fully developed spatiotemporal dynamics. These complex phenomena are attracting increasing interest in recent years [32,33], in particular, after the observation of spatiotemporal mode-locking in multimode optical fibers [34,35]. An overview of the applications of multimode photonics, where light is structured in both time and space, has recently appeared [36].

In this paper we realize a spatiotemporal mode-locked VECSEL, and we operate it in the regime of temporal LSs. The mode-locked pulses exhibit a spatial profile consisting of a combination of an axial plane wave with a set of tilted waves having a hexagonal arrangement in the Fourier space. These plane waves are phase locked, and their interference gives birth to a hexagonal pattern in the near-field emission profile. We show that these spatiotemporal mode-locked pulses can be individually addressed by shining short pump pulses; hence we call them temporal localized patterns. Our theoretical analysis reveals that they arise from a Turing instability whose critical wave vector is determined by spherical aberrations of the optical elements.

Fig. 1. (a) Experimental setup showing the L-shape VECSEL. d_1 , distance between the gain mirror and lens L_1 ; d_2 , distance between L_1 and lens L_2 ; d_3 , distance between L_2 and lens L_3 ; d_4 , distance between L_3 and lens L_4 ; d_5 , distance between L_4 and the SESAM; HRM, high-reflectivity beam splitter ($>99.5\%$ at $1.06 \mu\text{m}$). For the telecentric configuration, the distances are $d_1 = f_1$, $d_2 = f_1 + f_2$, $d_3 = f_2 + f_3$, $d_4 = f_3 + f_4$, and $d_5 = f_4$. (b) Calculated waist size of the fundamental Gaussian mode on the gain mirror as a function of the SESAM position x and for two positions of L_2 : $z = 2.5 \text{ mm}$ (blue curve) and $z = -3.5 \text{ mm}$ (red curve) when $f_{\text{th}} = 40 \text{ mm}$. x and z are the offsets of the SESAM and of L_2 with respect to their telecentric position: $x = d_5 - f_c$, $z = d_2 - (f_c + f_2)$. For $f_{\text{th}} = 40 \text{ mm}$, the SI condition is given by $z_0 = -0.8 \text{ mm}$, $x_0 = -1.3 \mu\text{m}$. Hence, in terms of $\Delta z = z - z_0$, $\Delta z = +3.3 \text{ mm}$ (blue curve) and $\Delta z = -2.7 \text{ mm}$ (red curve). These numerical curves obtained using Eqs. (S4) and (S5) of Supplement 1 fit with good agreement the experimentally measured values of w when the VECSEL is pumped at 230 mW for which the corresponding thermal lens is $f_{\text{th}} \approx 40 \text{ mm}$, as shown in Supplement 1.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

In this paper we design, realize, and operate a PML VECSEL fulfilling the large-aspect-ratio condition and, at the same time, hosting temporal LSs. While the former requires a broad-area pumped region and nearly self-imaging (SI) external cavity [13,14,37], temporal LSs appear from PML when the external cavity roundtrip is larger than the gain recovery time ($\tau > \tau_g$) and when modulation depth of the saturable absorber is above a critical value [28,31,38]. Accordingly, we consider an L-shaped VECSEL delimited by the gain mirror (also called 1/2 VCSEL) and by a semiconductor saturable absorber mirror (SESAM) [see Fig. 1(a)]. The gain mirror is optically pumped at 808 nm by a flat-top elliptical profile having a size of $90 \times 50 \mu\text{m}$ (see Supplement 1). Light extraction occurs through a highly reflective beam splitter ($>99.5\%$ reflectivity), which reflects the intracavity radiation. This L-shape geometry avoids the anisotropies that would have been introduced by using a transmitting splitter in a linear cavity. The output beam from the VECSEL is sent to the detection part where the far-field and near-field profiles are imaged on two CCD cameras. The near-field is also imaged on an array of optical fibers for spatially resolved detection at 10 GHz bandwidth. Finally, the total emission is monitored by a 33 GHz bandwidth detection system and by an optical spectrum analyzer.

The gain mirror is based on a GaAs substrate with 12 strain-balanced InGaAs/GaAsP quantum wells (QWs) designed for barrier optical pumping and emitting at $1.6 \mu\text{m}$. The SESAM features a single strained InGaAs/GaAs QW located near the external surface [39] leading to a recombination rate approximately two orders of magnitude faster than the gain medium. Details about the characteristics of these elements are given in Supplement 1.

The control parameters of the VECSEL are the pumping power P_p and the detuning $\delta\lambda$ between the microcavity resonance of the gain mirror (λ_G) and the one of the SESAM (λ_{SA}), $\delta\lambda = \lambda_{SA} - \lambda_G$. This detuning controls the amount of saturable losses experienced by the electromagnetic field inside the cavity whose value is crucial for obtaining bistability of the VECSEL close to threshold [31].

A. Design of the External Cavity and SI Condition

The VECSEL external cavity [see Fig. 1(a)] is designed to fulfill the requirement $\tau > \tau_g \sim 1 \text{ ns}$ and SI condition after one roundtrip. In addition, the SESAM and gain mirror need to be placed in

conjugate planes with a magnification factor M greater than unity for efficiently saturating the SESAM.

Accordingly we adopt a four-lens arrangement where the lens closest to the gain mirror (L_1) and the one closest to the SESAM (L_4) are large-numerical-aperture aspheric collimators ($f_1 = f_4 = f_c = 8 \text{ mm}$), while L_2 and L_3 are achromatic lenses having $f_2 = 100 \text{ mm}$ and $f_3 = 200 \text{ mm}$. In the cold cavity situation, the SI condition can be achieved through a telecentric arrangement of these optical elements; i.e., lenses are placed at distances given by the sum of their focal lengths, thus making a total cavity length $L = 632 \text{ mm}$ (cavity roundtrip time $\tau \approx 4.2 \text{ ns}$) and magnification given by $M = f_3/f_2 = 2$ (see Supplement 1).

However, the presence of a pump-induced lens [40] onto the gain mirror modifies significantly the positions of the lenses for achieving the SI condition with respect to the cold cavity situation. This spurious lens has a focal length f_{th} that depends on the pump intensity. As shown in Supplement 1, the SI condition requires us to offset the position of the SESAM and of L_2 with respect to their telecentric positions. By calling these offsets respectively x and z , the SI condition is given by $z = z_0 = -\frac{f_c^2}{2f_{\text{th}}}$ and $x = x_0 = -\frac{f_c^4}{2M^2 f_2^2 f_{\text{th}}}$. For our cavity z_0 is of the order of a few millimeters, while x_0 is of the order of a few micrometers.

From the experimental point of view, the precision requirement on the positions of the optical elements makes it unrealistic to achieve the SI condition by placing these elements at the calculated positions. It is then useful to calculate the ABCD roundtrip matrix in the presence of deviations from the SI condition that we quantify by introducing $\Delta x = x - x_0$ and $\Delta z = z - z_0$. The coefficients of this matrix, which are described in Supplement 1 [Eq. (S4)], can be used to calculate the waist w of the fundamental Gaussian beam on the gain mirror as a function of the positions of the SESAM and of L_2 around the SI condition. In Fig. 1(b) we plot w as a function of the position of the SESAM, and we can notice that the waist exhibits opposite behaviors depending on whether $\Delta z > 0$ or $\Delta z < 0$. For negative values of Δz [red curve in Fig. 1(b)], w increases when approaching the SESAM to L_4 . For $\Delta z > 0$ [blue curve in Fig. 1(b)] w increases with the distance between the SESAM and L_4 . This behavior is clearly observed in the experiment, and it enables an accurate observational assessment of the SI condition.

Fig. 2. (a) Near-field and (b) far-field time-averaged profiles of the patterns observed when $\Delta z = +3.3$ mm and $22 \mu\text{m} < x < 27 \mu\text{m}$. VECSEL is pumped at 320 mW and $\delta\lambda = 5$ nm. In panel (b), the far field has been obtained by filtering out the central part of the profile, which carries 90% of the total emitted intensity and it hides the off-axis components on the CCD camera. The unfiltered far-field profile is plotted in the inset. This kind of pattern is observed in the range $0.1 \text{ mm} < \Delta z < 4$ mm. As $|\Delta z| \rightarrow 0$, its existence range in x gets narrower and it requires a higher level of pumping. (c) Near-field profile with intensity peaks circled in red. (d) Near-field profile after filtering out the off-axis Fourier components of the pattern and leaving only the central spot. (e) Near-field profile after filtering out the on-axis Fourier components of the pattern (central spot in the far-field). The contours of the peaks of the total pattern identified in (c) are plotted in red.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

As shown in Fig. 1(b), the analysis of the waist of the fundamental Gaussian mode together with its experimental measurements allow us to determine the cavity parameters with respect to the SI condition. As $|\Delta x| \rightarrow 0$, the waist of the fundamental Gaussian decreases, and, when $|w| < 20 \mu\text{m}$, spatially extended patterns appear and cover the entire pumped section of the VECSEL. In Fig. 2 we show the time-averaged spatial profile of a typical pattern observed when $\Delta x \rightarrow 0^+$, for a finite positive value of Δz . This pattern cannot be interpreted as a transverse mode imposed by the boundaries of the resonator, such as the ones of the Hermite–Gauss or Laguerre–Gauss families [41]. While the latter self-transforms in the Fourier space, the pattern shown in Fig. 2 exhibits non-homothetic near-field and far-field profiles, as commonly observed in large-aspect-ratio resonators. The far-field profile reveals a bright central spot surrounded by a nearly hexagonal arrangement of weaker spots at 7° with respect to the optical axis of the resonator. In the near-field we observe a hexagonal pattern with some bright spots. We have analyzed the relationship between the near-field profile and each wave-vector component observed in the far-field, as shown in Figs. 2(c)–2(e). If we consider only the axial component (central spot in the far-field profile), the corresponding near-field profile has a Gaussian shape [Fig. 2(d)]. This component comprises 90% of the optical power of the pattern. If the central spot in the far-field is filtered out, the near-field profile obtained has twice the spatial frequency compared to the one obtained without the filter as can be observed in Fig. 2(e). This indicates that the near-field profile is determined by the interference between an on-axis plane wave and the hexagonal set of tilted

waves which are phase locked. The pattern shown in Fig. 2 is emitted by the VECSEL within a short range of x , for pumping powers $285 \text{ mW} < P_p < 400 \text{ mW}$ and for a detuning range between the microcavity resonances $4.5 \text{ nm} < \delta\lambda < 8 \text{ nm}$. Within these ranges, the time-averaged profile shown in Fig. 2 is not affected significantly by parameter changes.

The time behavior of the pattern of Fig. 2 is shown in Fig. 3(a). It features multistability between a set of mode-locked states with a number of pulses per roundtrip ranging from zero to five. The corresponding bifurcation diagram of these pulsating solutions versus the pump power P_p is explored in Fig. 3(b). Upon increasing the pumping level (P_p), the off solution loses its stability at $P_p = 320$ mW in favor of a five-pulses per roundtrip mode-locked state. Then, by decreasing P_p , the VECSEL emission switches to states with a lower number of pulses per roundtrip and, when $P_p < 285$ mW, the VECSEL switches to the off solution. At every downward jump P_p is increased to explore the stability of the pulsating solution as a function of the pump. The width of the pulses emitted is below the time resolution of our detection system (10 ps rise time, 33 GHz), as shown in Supplement 1. Auto-correlation measurements of the electromagnetic field give a coherence time of the pulse of 2.6 ps. In Fig. 3(c) we show the optical spectra for each pulsing state shown in Fig. 3(a). It is worth noting that the resolution of the optical spectrum analyzer (0.06 nm, i.e., 15 GHz) does not allow us to resolve the spectral combs corresponding to the mode-locked state shown in Fig. 3(a) whose teeth separation is in the range of 0.25–1.25 GHz (see Fig. S5 in Supplement 1). On the other hand, the width of the spectral envelopes (≈ 1 nm, FWHM) confirms the coherence time measured through auto-correlation.

Fig. 3. Spatially integrated intensity output of the pattern shown in Fig. 2. (a) Coexisting pulsating states of the pattern. (b) Total output power emitted by the VECSEL versus the pump power P_p for different pulsating states of the pattern, ranging from no pulse to five pulses per roundtrip (detection bandwidth 10 GHz). (c) Optical spectra corresponding to different pulsating states of the pattern. We notice that the peaks of the spectra of different N_p scale as P_{out} does in panel (b) for the corresponding N_p .

While Fig. 3(a) shows the total intensity output of the pattern, we have also performed spatially resolved acquisitions by monitoring synchronously different points of the pattern. These spatially resolved time traces, together with phase correlation measurements, both shown in Supplement 1, reveal that the whole pattern is pulsating as a unique coherent structure.

The multistability between different mode-locked states shown in Fig. 3 indicates that the patterns observed are temporal LSs; i.e., they are individually addressable pulses traveling back and forth in the external cavity [28,30]. Addressing temporal LSs has been demonstrated in driven Kerr-cavities [23,25] by using optical pulses that are coherent with the driving field. In our optically pumped VECSEL, temporal LSs can be individually addressed by shining short pump pulses onto the gain mirror. The system is set by the CW optical pump in the multistable parameter region ($285 \text{ mW} < P_p < 318 \text{ mW}$) where LSs exist. An additional laser, capable of providing optical pulses of about 120 ps (FWHM) at arbitrary rate, is used to generate pump pulses that are overlapped to the CW pump. These pulses have a Gaussian spatial profile and a waist of $13 \mu\text{m}$, which matches approximately the waist of the Gaussian on-axis component of the pattern [Fig. 2(d)]. The pulse peak power is chosen to be sufficiently large to drive the VECSEL beyond the upper limit of the multistable region shown in Fig. 3(b), where only the solution composed of five pulses per roundtrip is stable. Finally, the addressing pulse is sent to the gain mirror synchronously with the cavity roundtrip for about 5000 roundtrips. The addressing process is depicted in Fig. 4 by using a space-time diagram where the pump value is represented using a color code, while the trajectory of the LS is represented by a black trace. In Fig. 4(a), we choose an initial condition where no LS is present inside the cavity before the addressing pulse. The pump pulse is sufficiently short to switch on a single LS that persists after the perturbation is removed. In Fig. 4(b) we repeat the operation with a LS already existing in the cavity before the addressing pulse. Other initial conditions can be chosen with similar results, provided that the addressing pulse is separated in time from the

preexisting LS of at least τ_c . This addressing technique can be adapted for erasing LSs. In this case we apply downward pulses to the pump, which, for a short time window, bring the VECSEL in the monostable region, where only the off solution is stable. The switching off procedure is shown in Fig. 4(c). Erasure of LSs can be also obtained by feeding back an emitted pulse onto the gain mirror with proper time delay, as described in [42].

4. DISCUSSION AND THEORETICAL ANALYSIS

Our experimental results provide evidence of a novel spatiotemporal laser regime, which, to the best of our knowledge, can hardly be traced back to any laser model in the literature. Stationary pattern emission from large-aspect-ratio lasers has been previously observed and explained as a Turing instability leading to transverse traveling waves [10,11,43]. The physical origin of this instability has been attributed to the presence of a (positive) detuning between the gain curve resonance and the closest resonator resonance. The laser emits tilted waves whose frequency matches the gain resonance and whose longitudinal wave vector fulfills the resonance condition of the resonator. This mechanism is not relevant in our system where the set of longitudinal cavity resonances is very dense (less than 500 MHz free spectral range) compared to the width of all other relevant spectral filtering curves, such as microcavity resonances ($>9 \text{ nm}$, i.e., more than 1 THz), gain, and saturable absorption curves (more than 10 THz).

In order to describe the spatiotemporal dynamics observed, we could employ the Haus master equation for PML adapted to the long cavity limit [30,44]. However, this leads to a four-dimensional, stiff, multi-scale PDE.

We have chosen instead to use a simpler model accounting for the essential physical mechanisms underlying the observed spatiotemporal dynamics. While we cannot expect this model to be quantitatively accurate, we will show that it can reproduce the experimental findings with good qualitative agreement.

Fig. 4. Spatiotemporal diagrams of the writing and erasing processes of a temporal localized pattern. The trajectory of the LS is represented by a black trace, while the pump evolution is represented on the space-time diagram by using a color code. (a), (b) The stationary value of the pump is $P_p = 312$ mW and addressing is obtained by sending a 120 ps pump pulse, 10 mW peak power onto the gain mirror between roundtrip $n_1 = 7800$ and roundtrip $n_2 = 12500$ in panel (a) and between roundtrip $n_1 = 6800$ and roundtrip $n_2 = 12500$ in panel (b). (c) The stationary value of the pump is $P_p = 293$ mW and addressing is obtained by sending a negative 800 ps pump pulse onto the gain mirror between roundtrip $n_1 = 8640$ and roundtrip $n_2 = 13200$. A negative pulse decreases the pump level down to $P_p = 283$ mW.

This model for the dynamics of the transverse profile of temporal LSs can be obtained adapting New's method of PML [45] to the situation at hand. This method, already used in [46,47], exploits the scale separation between the pulse evolution, the so-called fast stage in which stimulated emission is dominant, and the slow stage that is controlled by the gain recovery processes. Under the hypothesis that the spatiotemporal profile can be factored into a product of a transverse profile and a short temporal pulse that corresponds to the temporal LS, one can obtain a simplified description of the slow evolution of the transverse profile of the temporal LS $A(r_\perp, \theta)$ as

$$\frac{\partial A}{\partial \theta} = [f(|A|^2) + \mathcal{L}_\perp] A, \quad (1)$$

where θ is the roundtrip number and we defined the effective nonlinearity as

$$f(P) = (1 - i\alpha_1)J_1(r_\perp)b(P) + (1 - i\alpha_2)J_2b(sP) - k. \quad (2)$$

The nonlinear response of the active material to a pulse is $b(p) = (1 - e^{-p})/p$. We define k as the roundtrip cavity loss, and in Eq. (2) we introduced the line-width enhancement factors α_j of the two active media, which relax toward the pumping power J_j . The ratio of the saturation fluences of the absorber and of the gain is denoted by the parameter s . The effect of finite size optical pumping is taken into account by the spatial dependence of $J_1(r_\perp) > 0$. Saturable absorption is obtained by setting $J_2 < 0$. It is worth noting that, if the function $b(P)$ is replaced by the Lorentzian line saturation for continuous wave beams $b(P) \rightarrow 1/(1 + P)$ in Eqs. (1) and (2), one obtains the equations described in [19,48], used for describing (stationary) spatial auto-solitons in continuous wave bistable interferometers.

The spatiotemporal linear operator \mathcal{L}_\perp can be determined by using the Fresnel transform [49], which permits the analytical calculation of the transverse effects occurring at each roundtrip from the roundtrip ABCD matrix. The latter includes diffraction and wavefront curvature occurring in the quasi-telecentric cavity as well as diffraction and thermal lensing (in the parabolic approximation) taking place within the microcavities. In addition, we considered the influence of weak spherical aberrations. The latter are essentially due to the presence of the two short focal distances collimators L1 and L4, which are challenged by the wide angular spread of the beams. In agreement with experimental observations, we assume that $f_c(r_\perp) = f_0 + \sigma r_\perp^2$ with $\sigma \ll 1$ representing

a small aberration coefficient. For the experimental conditions (nearly SI condition and $f_0/f_{2,3} \ll 1$), the effect of spherical aberration can be analytically reduced to a transverse Bilaplacian operator. The details of these calculations will be discussed elsewhere. Describing the wavefront curvature, the diffraction, and aberrations as small perturbations to the field profile at each roundtrip, the spatiotemporal linear operator \mathcal{L}_\perp reads

$$\mathcal{L}_\perp = i\tilde{C}r_\perp^2 + (d + i\tilde{B})\nabla_\perp^2 + i\tilde{S}\nabla_\perp^4, \quad (3)$$

where we define the following parameters: the effective diffraction parameter $\tilde{B} = \lambda B_{RT}/(4\pi) + l_{1,\perp}^2 + l_{2,\perp}^2$, the wavefront curvature $\tilde{C} = \pi C_{RT}/\lambda$, and the aberration parameter $\tilde{S} = (\frac{\lambda}{2\pi})^3 \sigma f_0^2$. Here, B_{RT} and C_{RT} are the off diagonal elements of the round-trip matrix and $l_{j,\perp}$ are the microcavity diffraction lengths. As shown by Eq. (S6) in Supplement 1, close to SI conditions, $B_{RT} \approx 2(M^2 \Delta x)$ and $C_{RT} \approx -2\frac{\Delta z}{f_c}$, so Δx controls the diffraction while Δz rules the wavefront curvature, which is equivalent to a parabolic transverse potential in Eq. (3). The finite size of lenses and the numerical aperture of the whole optical system are modeled by a diffusion parameter d that penalizes high transverse spatial frequencies q_\perp .

Close to the SI condition, for positive diffraction ($\Delta x \gtrsim 0$), the VECSEL resonator is stable for focusing wavefront curvature ($\tilde{C} \lesssim 0$, i.e., $\Delta z \gtrsim 0$). Experimental results show that, when $\tilde{B} \rightarrow 0$, a modulated pattern featuring well-defined transverse wave vectors appears. This phenomenology can be explained as the result of a supercritical Turing instability. It was shown in [50] that Eq. (1) forbids the appearance of a Turing instability, while it allows for a long wavelength instability and the formation of a band of unstable spatial frequencies in the range $q \in [0, q_M]$. However, the presence of the Bilaplacian operator describing optical aberrations changes this picture, as it introduces a new spatial scale in the system and it renders the appearance of a Turing bifurcation possible. This is shown in Fig. 5(a) where we plot the result of the stability analysis of the homogeneous state for a value of the pump within the bistability region where the VECSEL emits temporal LS. The real part of the two dominant eigenvalues reveals the presence of a Turing instability at a wave vector $q_T \simeq \sqrt{\tilde{B}/\tilde{S}}$ in addition to the band of unstable spatial frequencies in the range $q \in [0, q_M]$. It is worth noting that the finite size of the pump profile imposes a low-frequency cutoff for the wave vectors allowed in the system,

Fig. 5. (a) Stability analysis of the uniform solution over the upper state of the bistable solution branch. A long wavelength modulational instability band is present; however, it is inhibited for a system size of $L_{\perp} = 8.3776$, which corresponds to a low-frequency cutoff of $q_c = 2\pi/L_{\perp} = 0.75$ (orange vertical dashed line). A second narrow band that corresponds to a Turing instability may appear at a wave vector $q_T \simeq \sqrt{\tilde{B}/\tilde{S}} = 3.01$. This diagram is obtained after the emergence of the Turing instability for a value of $J_1 = 0.78J_{\text{th}}$ that corresponds to an intensity $I = 1$. It is above the fold located at $J_F \simeq 0.661J_{\text{th}}$. (b) Branch of CW (blue) and spatially periodic (red) solutions of Eq. (1). The intensity of the field is shown as a function of the scaled gain bias J_1/J_{th} . The stable (unstable) solutions are depicted as solid (dashed) lines. The unstable CW branch bifurcates from the off state, and it is stabilized at the fold F after a sequence of Andronov-Hopf bifurcations (red squares). The stable periodic branch that corresponds to rolls bifurcates from the CW solution at the branching point BP (black circle), which corresponds to a Turing bifurcation. The emerging pattern further loses its stability via an Andronov-Hopf bifurcation (red square). The two insets show the intensity of the emerging periodic pattern at the points marked as green diamonds. (c) Equivalent regime in two dimensions where we show the intensity profile as well as the far-field Fourier spectrum after removal of the on-axis homogeneous component (inset). It consists in a regular hexagonal pattern whose wave vector ($|q_T| \simeq 3$) is given by the stability analysis of the uniform state. The bias current is $J_1 = 0.777J_{\text{th}}$ and $(L_x, L_y) = (8.378, 7.255)$. Other common parameters are $\tilde{B} = 1$, $\tilde{C} = 0$, $S = 0.11$, $\alpha_1 = 1.5$, $\alpha_2 = 0.5$, $J_2 = -0.12$, $k = 0.1$, $s = 15$, $d = 0.003$.

$q_c = 2\pi/L_{\perp}$. This spatial frequency filtering eventually controls which instability can develop: if $q_M < q_c$ the long wavelength instability is inhibited and the Turing pattern remains the unique spatial instability that can emerge, provided that q_T is resonant, i.e., an integer multiple of q_c , i.e., with $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Consequently, this instability can be expected to appear by tuning the value of \tilde{B} within a narrow range, in good agreement with experimental observations.

In Fig. 5(b) we show the result of numerical simulations of Eq. (1) as well as path continuation using Pde2Path [51] for a system with one transverse spatial dimension and with homogeneous pumping; see Supplement 1 for more details. It reveals that a homogeneous emission of temporal LSs appears subcritically below the lasing threshold. The corresponding C-shape is represented by the blue line in Fig. 5(b). When the system size is chosen such that $q_T/q_c = 4$, a periodic pattern can emerge from a homogeneous emission while increasing the pump power. As in the experiment, the periodic pattern appears as a modulation of a homogeneous on-axis emission that dominates the far-field profile. This Turing pattern can be observed at a fixed pump level by tuning the value \tilde{B} , as this parameter will change the value of the critical wave vector q_T with respect to $4q_c$. In this case the pattern will appear with a finite modulation amplitude of the homogeneous emission, fixed by the pump power. In two transverse dimensions, the dynamics is more complex since only the magnitude of the unstable wave vector $|q_T|$ is fixed by the linear stability analysis leading to an annular distribution of unstable wave vectors in the two-dimensional plane spanned by $q_{\perp} = (q_x, q_y)$. Stripes, squares, or hexagonal patterns can be selected depending on the kind of nonlinearity coupling the different wave vectors that must all emerge with magnitude $|q_T|$ [1,52]. However, the structure of the nonlinearity in Eq. (1) favors the emergence of hexagonal patterns as can be seen in Fig. 5(c). The far-field represented in the inset of Fig. 5(c) exhibits (in log scale) the typical spectrum associated with hexagonal patterns after filtering out the on-axis

component. The value of $q_T \sim 3$ matches the result of the linear stability analysis.

In conclusion, we have realized and operated a laser platform enabling the investigation of fully developed spatiotemporal dynamics. In this paper, we have operated it in the regime of spatiotemporal mode-locking, and we have reported, to the best of our knowledge, the first observation of temporal localized Turing patterns, but other novel laser regimes will be investigated in the future, including the generation of spatiotemporal LS, also called dissipative light bullets [46]. The theoretical analysis has revealed the important role of optical aberrations when approaching the SI condition, thus suggesting that spatial control of light in our VECSEL will demand aberration engineered optical elements and/or counterbalancing nonlinear effects. An alternative path is based on the introduction of spatially patterned laser parameters. In particular, the spatial shaping of the pumped region opens interesting perspectives since, thanks to the SI condition, the pump pattern will be reproduced in the near-field emission of the laser. This can be achieved, for example, by depositing an absorptive mask onto the gain mirror. Preliminary results indicate the possibility of implementing spatially decorrelated sources of temporal LS in a single VECSEL. As illustrated in [36], several applications can be envisaged for the VECSEL we have studied in this paper. Among them we underline spatiotemporal processing of information, frequency comb multiplexing in the same cavity [53], and speckle-free imaging with short pulses [54].

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Supplemental document. See [Supplement 1](#) for supporting content.

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